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OVERVIEW OF STRESS LEVEL AND FACTOR ANALYSIS CAUSES OF STRESS IN THE ELDERLY GROUP *CASE STUDY: ELDERLY GROUP OF ST. ANGELA SAMARINDA*

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ABSTRACT

Stress is an imbalance of self/spirit and the reality of everyday life that cannot be avoided or changes that require adjustment. Humans develop from helplessness to become perfect and independent human beings and finally become old and helpless again. The elderly experience gradual physical and psychological decline and the decline in these conditions can cause stress for some of the elderly. This study aims to describe the level of stress and analyze the factors that cause stress in the elderly in Samarinda. This research is descriptive qualitative, the study population is all the elderly in St. Angela Samarinda as many as 35 people. Data collection is done through the results of observation and interviews. The results showed that (1) out of 35 respondents, 8 respondents (22.90%) experienced very heavy stress, 10 respondents (28.50%) experienced severe stress, 3 respondents (8.60%) experienced mild stress and 5 respondents (14.30%) experienced moderate stress; and (2) The dominant causes of stress are a limited economy and the emergence of chronic diseases, followed by a decrease in physical strength, lifestyle changes, feeling depressed due to the death of a spouse and feeling lonely.

KEYWORDS:

Elderly, Stress.St. Angela Samarinda

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INTRODUCTION

Aging is a natural process, aging will occur in all systems of the human body and not all systems will experience setbacks at the same time. Even though the process of aging is a universal picture, no one knows for sure the causes of aging or why people grow old at different ages [1].

According to WHO, an elderly person is someone who has entered the age of 60 years and over. According to [2] that the elderly are the age group in humans who have entered the final stages of their life and will experience a process called the aging process. [3] states that geriatric age is grouped into three age limits, namely age 70–75 years (young-old), age 75–80 years (old), and age over 80 years (very old). old).

Based on census data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2015, the elderly population in Indonesia numbered 25.48 million people (8.03%), then in 2020 it is expected to increase to 28.8 million people (11.34%).

Humans develop from helplessness to become perfect and independent human beings and finally become old and helpless again. However, some people are afraid and don't want to accept the reality and don't know how to deal with their old age. How many elderly people feel lonely and useless, and not a few experience stress [4].

Stress is an imbalance of self/spirit and the reality of everyday life that cannot be avoided or changes that require adjustment.

Often perceived as a negative event or change that can cause stress, such as an injury, illness, or death of a loved one. The impact that occurs when a person experiences stress is on his psychological condition, where the psychological problem that is often experienced by the elderly is loneliness. The National Council on Aging and Older People reports that the prevalence of loneliness in America is quite high, with 62% of the elderly [5]. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the percentage of elderly who experience mild loneliness is 69%, moderate loneliness is 11%, severe loneliness is 2%, and the remaining 16% do not experience loneliness [6].

Older humans will experience gradual physical and psychological decline, where a decrease in these conditions can cause stress. The elderly must adapt to various changes both physically, mentally, and socially. The life changes that must be faced by elderly individuals in particular have the potential to cause stress.

[7] states that stress in terms of its causes is divided into two kinds, namely macro causes and micro causes. Macro causes, namely related to major life events, such as death, divorce, retirement, emotional pain, and bankruptcy. Meanwhile, micro causes, which involve small daily events, such as household fights, workload, and problems with what to eat.

The elderly group in Santa Angela is an initiative of the community to form an elderly association and become a group with the name Santa Angela, this group is under the auspices of the Eternal Helper Santa Maria Catholic Church, namely the Samarinda Cathedral. The number of members is 50 people, but the active ones sometimes range from 30 to 40 people. The routine activities of this group are health check-ups and health counseling. It is hoped that knowing the level of stress and stress-causing factors in the elderly, will be able to become a source of information in developing intervention programs to improve the welfare of the elderly so that they remain happy and prosperous in their old age.

The research objective was to describe the level of stress and analyze the factors that cause stress in the elderly in Samarinda.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research was conducted from February to June 2023 at the St. Angela Samarinda (St. Maria Perpetual Help Cathedral Parish). According to [8] that population is a group of subjects who will be subject to generalization of research results consisting of some individuals who at least have the same traits or characteristics. In this study, the research sample was all elderly who took part in routine activities at the Santa Angela Group at the Samarinda Cathedral, totaling 35 people.

This study used the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale 42 instrument which was changed to 20 questions related to stress in general (physical and psychological). Data collection is done through the results of observation and interviews. Data

analysis was carried out using descriptive statistical analysis which intended to describe stress levels and stress-causing factors in the elderly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Overview of Stress Levels

The results of the study regarding the description of stress levels in the elderly at St. Angela Samarinda are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of Stress Levels in the Elderly St. Angela Samarinda

Stress Level	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
No Stress	9	25,70
Light Stress	3	8,60
Moderate Stress	5	14,30
Heavy Stress	10	28,50
Extremely Stressful	8	22,90
Total	35	100,00

Source: Data Processed Results (2023)

Table 1 above shows that of the 35 respondents in this study, it was shown that 8 respondents (22.90%) experienced very heavy stress, 10 respondents (28.50%) experienced severe stress, 10 respondents (28.50%) experienced mild stress and 8 people (22.90%) were moderately stressed and 9 people (25.70%) did not experience stress. The results of this study indicate that most of the elderly (respondents), 18 people (51.40%), fall into the categories of severe stress and very severe stress. The results of this study are in line with research reported by [9], that is, of 32 elderly people at the Pucang Gading Wredha Panti Semarang showed a high-stress level of 81.25% showed severe complaints, and only 18.75% showed moderate complaints. The elderly who experience severe and very severe stress are influenced by several causal factors, both past experiences and the realities of life that are currently being experienced. [10] states that stress in the elderly can be interpreted as an unbalanced condition, unpleasant pressure, or disturbance, which occurs throughout the body and can affect life, which is created when the person concerned sees a mismatch between the situation and the system. biological, psychological, and social resources related to thinking and responding to threats and dangers in the elderly. Where there is a decrease in the ability to maintain life,

adapt to the environment, body, and psychological functions naturally and which can eventually result in death.

2. Description of the Causes of Stress

The results of research regarding the causes of stress in the elderly at St. Angela Samarinda are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Description of the causes of stress in the elderly in Santa Angela Samarinda

Causes of Stress	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
Lifestyle Changes Interfered with My Daily Life	28	80,00
Limited Economy Boggles the Mind	30	85,71
Feeling Depressed Due to the Death Of a Partner	27	77,14
The Emergence Of a Disturbing Chronic Disease	30	85,71
Decreased Physical Strength	29	82,86
Unsupportive Family Environment	21	60,00
Caring for a Sick Partner	22	62,86
Burdened with Caring for Grandchildren	22	62.86
Lonely	24	69,57

Source: Data Processed Results (2023)

The results of the study in Table 2 above show that the description of the causes of stress from 35 respondents is as follows 30 respondents (85.71%) stated that the main causes of stress in the elderly are a limited economy and the emergence of chronic diseases. The second cause of stress is a decrease in physical strength, namely 29 respondents (82.86%). Then the third cause is a lifestyle change as many as 28 respondents (80.00%). Furthermore, there were 27 respondents (77.14%) who felt depressed due to the death of their spouse. Some respondents felt lonely as many as 24 respondents (69.57%). The last causal factor, namely caring for a spouse who is sick and burdened with caring for grandchildren, obtained the same score as many as 22 respondents (62.86%) and an unsupportive environment for as many as 21 respondents (60.00%). The results of this study are

in line with the results of research conducted by [9] on the elderly at the Pucang Gading Semarang Wredha Panti, namely the five major causes of stress were found, changes in daily activities, changes in family associations, death of a spouse, death of members family and changes in choice and quantity of sport and recreation. Based on the results of studies conducted [11]. found 109 elderly (94 elderly women and 15 elderly men) who were in one of the working areas of the Puskesmas in Semarang City, most of these elderly stated that the cause of stress experienced was due to several factors such as illness, loss of loved ones, raising grandchildren, lack of family support and economic problems. Psychological complaints such as irritability, sometimes feeling sad, feeling helpless, and feeling useless are also felt by the elderly. Stress is one of the psychosocial problems where life pressures and unhealthy lifestyles, as well as various illnesses that are being suffered, can trigger stress. The results of another study reported by [12] that the stress experienced by the elderly is influenced by several factors, including current illness, loss of loved ones, lack of family support, raising grandchildren, and economic problems.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion it can be concluded that:

1. Out of 35 respondents, 8 respondents (22.90%) experienced very heavy stress, 10 respondents (28.50%) experienced severe stress, 3 respondents (8.60%) experienced mild stress and 5 respondents (14.30%) experienced moderate stress.
2. The dominant stress-causing factors are a limited economy and the emergence of chronic diseases, followed by a decrease in physical strength, lifestyle changes, feeling depressed due to the death of a spouse, and feeling lonely.

B. Suggestion

For senior management groups to be able to carry out further research and counseling regularly to reduce stress levels, then routine meetings are not only filled with health checks and counseling but can be interspersed with group therapy or entertainment activities.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Fatmawati, V and M. A. Imron. 2017. Coping Behavior in the Elderly with Decreased Movement and Function. *Intuition, Journal of Scientific Psychology* 9(1):26–38.
- [2] Sunaryo. et al. 2015. *Gerontic Nursing Care*. Andi Offset, Semarang.
- [3] Azizah, LilikMa'rifatul. 2011. *Elderly Nursing*. Science House. Yogyakarta.
- [4] Rahman, S. 2016. Factors Underlying Stress in the Elderly. *Indonesian Education Journal* 16 (1): 1–7.
- [5] Damayanti, Y., Sukmono, AC. 2013. Differences in the Levels of Loneliness in Elderly Living in Nursing Homes and Homes with Families. *E-Journal*:1–10.
- [6] Indonesian Ministry of Health. 2013. *Health Data and Information Window Bulletin: Overview of Elderly Health in Indonesia*. Jakarta: Department of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. Retrieved December 18, 2022
- [7] Brecht, G. 2000. *Monograph Recognizing and coping with stress*. Prenhalindo, Jakarta.
- [8] Azwar, S. 2001. *Research Methods*. Offset Student Library, Yogyakarta.
- [9] Indriana, Y., I. F. Kristiana., A.A. Sonda, Dan A. Intanirian. 2019. Elderly Stress Levels at the “Pucang Gading” Nursing Home Semarang. *Journal of Psychology Undip Semarang* 8 (2): 87–95.
- [10] Hidayah, N. 2013. Stress in the Elderly Becomes a Cause and Effect of Disease. *The Journal of Health Sciences* 6 (2): 1–8
- [11] Nugroho, A. S. & Purwanti SO. 2010. The relationship between stress levels and blood sugar levels in patients with diabetes mellitus in the working area of the Sukoharjo I Public Health Center, Sukoharjo Regency', *E-Journal FIK UMS*.
- [12] Kurniawati, D.A., M.S. Adi, and R. H. Widyastuti. 2020. Stress Levels in Elderly with Non-Communicable Diseases. *Journal of Psychiatric Nursing*. 8(2):123–128.